

ASAP

A Systemic APProach to social media
and pre-adolescents through thinking

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME
LEARNING UNIT

ROLE MODELS

Shaping values in the digital age

Co-funded by
the European Union

ROLE MODELS:
Shaping values in the digital age
LEARNING UNIT

Erasmus+ Programme

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ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

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R3.2.1 ASAP Educational Programme Handbook

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Learning Unit

Role Models: Shaping values in the digital age

FOCUS OF THIS UNIT

Introduction

Raising children in today's society presents a thrilling yet demanding experience, particularly for parents and educators dedicated to instilling strong values in 11 to 13-year-olds. This pivotal developmental phase is characterized by heightened curiosity, the formation of identity, and an increasing desire for belonging, making the values they embrace especially important. Core principles such as honesty, kindness, resilience, respect, and responsibility serve as essential guides for children as they navigate their lives. However, in our digital era, children are significantly influenced by online figures, known as *digital influencers*, who often act as contemporary role models.

These digital influencers hold considerable sway over children's behaviours, aspirations, and perspectives, shaping their understanding of success, relationships, and self-worth. While some influencers promote positive ideals like empathy, hard work, and social justice, others may model materialism, vanity, or unhealthy behaviours. This is where parents and educators play a vital role as guides and mentors, helping children critically evaluate the content they consume and aligning it with enduring values. Parents and educators can work together to inspire children to look up to influencers who promote creativity, community involvement, and resilience, rather than those focused on superficial achievements. By embodying and reinforcing these values, adults can cultivate a supportive environment that balances digital engagement with real-world ethical grounding.

Key Competences

Key Competences* (which the Unit aims to contribute to)	
General	Specific
PERSONAL: Self-regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Awareness and expression of personal emotions, thoughts, values, and behaviour.
PERSONAL: Wellbeing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Understanding potential risks for wellbeing and using reliable information and services for health and social protection.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adoption of a sustainable lifestyle that respects the environment, and the physical and mental wellbeing of self and others, while seeking and offering social support.
SOCIAL: Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness of another person's emotions, experiences and values. Responsiveness to another person's emotions and experiences, being conscious that group belonging influences one's attitude.
SOCIAL: Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intention to contribute to the common good and awareness that others may have different cultural affiliations, backgrounds, beliefs, values, opinions or personal circumstances.
LEARNING TO LEARN: Critical Thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness of potential biases in the data and one's personal limitations, while collecting valid and reliable information and ideas from diverse and reputable sources. Comparing, analysing, assessing, and synthesising data, information, ideas, and media messages in order to draw logical conclusions.
DIGITAL: Information and data literacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluating data, information and digital content
DIGITAL: Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protecting health and wellbeing

**Defined according to the LifeComp and DigComp 2.2 Frameworks*

Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes	
Knowledge	Skills and Abilities
Distinguishing between influencers as digital role models and parents as traditional role models, including the qualities and values each tends to promote.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critically compare the influence of digital role models with the values learned from parents, identifying the long-term impact each can have on their personal development.
Explaining social comparison theory and how influencers' idealized lives set unrealistic expectations for beauty, success, and happiness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spot edited or exaggerated content and practice distinguishing between online images and real-life situations to avoid negative self-comparisons.
Explaining the role of influencers in promoting viral challenges and the peer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Make independent, thoughtful decisions about participation without feeling the need to conform.

pressure that accompanying these trends, including the potential risks involved.	
Explaining how influencers impact their behaviour, choices, and self-perception, fostering more mindful engagement with social media.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resist to the negative social comparison, peer pressure, and the pressure to conform to unrealistic standards promoted by influencers.

Work plan

Topic 1: Importance of values		
Phase 1 (Knowledge building and skills development)	Activity 1.a.1: Exploring values in our lives Objective: To empower participants to recognize, understand, and evaluate different types of values and to become aware of their role in everyday life.	45 min
	Activity 1.a.2: Identifying values behind role models Objective: To explore the differences in how traditional and digital role models communicate specific values and their influence on young audiences.	45 min
Topic 2: Comparing traditional and digital role models		
Phase 2a (Knowledge building and skills development)	Activity 2.a.1: Similarities and differences between traditional and digital role models Objective: To distinguish between the values represented and shared by traditional and digital role models.	30 min
	Activity 2.a.2: Digital role models and social comparison Objective: To raise awareness of the influence of influencers on satisfaction with one's own body and lifestyle.	45 min
Phase 2b (Knowledge building and skills development)	Activity 2.b.1: Viral challenge match-up Objective: To raise awareness and differentiate between forms of viral challenges.	30 min
	Activity 2.b.2: Challenge accepted? Evaluating safety in viral trends Objective: To recognize and distinguish between short-term and long-term consequences of participating in a viral challenge.	45 min

	<p>Activity 2.b.3: Debunking influencer and viral challenges myths</p> <p>Objective: To raise awareness and critically evaluate the security and the positive and negative sides of the challenges in which digital influencers participate.</p>	30 min
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Final products

The final product of this learning unit is a raised level of awareness (through all the analysed worksheets) of kids about the values represented by traditional and digital role models, and an awareness of the values that are truly important in life. Kids will also become aware of the safety of viral challenges, especially those encouraged by digital role models themselves, and create a list of safety guidelines for evaluating viral challenges.

Evaluation

Objective:

Assess knowledge, skills, and attitudes gained from the activities, considering both immediate and longer-term effects.

Methods and tools:

Test (scenario on designing a safe, values-based viral challenge); self-evaluation questions; reality task ("My values journey" diary and analysis/presentation of a challenge or influencer trend).

Timing:

During/after activities and over the week-long "My values journey" project.

Roles:

Kids complete the test, self-evaluation, diary and presentation/video; the educator evaluates responses and products.

For detailed guidance on what and how to assess, as well as examples of possible assessment tools and criteria, educators can refer to the evaluation table below.

HOW	WHAT	EXAMPLE
TEST	Knowledge, skills	<p>Scenario: "Imagine you're designing a viral challenge for a campaign promoting positive social values (e.g., kindness, teamwork, or environmental awareness). What elements would you include to make it engaging and safe?"</p> <p>Instructions for kids: List at least 3 values your challenge will promote. Describe the steps of the challenge and explain how it avoids risks (both short-term and long-</p>

		<p>term). Identify how participants could share their results responsibly on social media.</p> <p>Educator's role: Evaluate their responses based on creativity, clarity, understanding of safety, and alignment with values.</p>
SELF-EVALUATION QUESTIONS	Knowledge, attitudes	<p>Which values do you find most important in your everyday life, and how do they guide your actions?</p> <p>How has your view of influencers or social media changed after these activities?</p> <p>What have you learned about the influence of viral challenges on decision-making?</p> <p>Describe a time when you felt peer pressure. How would you handle a similar situation now?</p> <p>What will you do differently in your interactions with online content or trends moving forward?</p>
REALITY TASK	Knowledge, skills, attitudes	<p>Kids will engage in a week-long project by maintaining a "My values journey". Their task is to document real-life situations that reflect their decision-making processes influenced by their values. Each diary entry should include the following components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A concise description of the scenario encountered. • Identification of the specific value(s) that influenced their decision. • An exploration of their feelings regarding the choice made. • A summary of what they learned from the experience and how it may affect future decisions. <p>This activity not only encourages kids to apply their understanding of values in practical contexts but also fosters critical thinking and self-reflection, essential skills for their personal development.</p> <p>Kids identify a viral challenge or influencer trend they've encountered. They create a short presentation or video explaining what the challenge involves, its potential risks and benefits, how it aligns (or doesn't align) with their values, and propose alternative ways to promote the same value or message without the risks.</p>

Application contexts

The activities in this learning unit are designed to be flexible and adaptable in various contexts and settings.

Classroom use:

These activities can be integrated into various subjects like Citizenship, Social Studies, ICT, or Media Literacy.

Library programs:

Libraries, both in schools and communities, are excellent spaces to introduce and discuss media, digital literacy, and citizenship. The activities can be adapted as independent sessions to engage kids or library visitors in these important topics.

Family and community engagement:

The learning unit can also be utilized in family or community workshops, encouraging broader participation. These sessions provide an opportunity for families to deepen their understanding of media and digital literacy while reinforcing the lessons kids are learning in school.

Links with other LUs

- **Authenticity & Authority:** analyses coherence, credibility, and authority in admired figures.
- **Communication:** focuses on how role models communicate values and shape peer influence.
- **Emotions:** links inspiration, empathy, and self-awareness to personal choices and behaviour.
- **Onlife:** explores how online presence and platforms amplify the visibility and impact of role models.

WHAT YOU NEED TO KNOW

Digital childhood and the rise of influencers

Children today grow up surrounded by digital technology. They frequently use smartphones, tablets, and computers, and spend much time on social media, messaging apps, and online games. Consequently, influencers have become new role models. They build significant followings on platforms like YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram, sharing everyday life or specialized interests like fashion, gaming, fitness, travel, or humor.

Influencers as relatable role models

In many ways, influencers have taken on roles traditionally held by family members or peer mentors. Unlike mainstream celebrities, influencers often appear more relatable to young viewers, which can make their influence even more potent. Children between the ages of 11 and 13 are particularly impressionable, and they often turn to influencers for entertainment, advice, inspiration, and identity formation. Many children report following influencers because they share common interests or help alleviate boredom (Coates et al., 2020). For example, boys might watch gaming influencers to learn strategies or discover new games, while others might follow beauty or lifestyle influencers to learn about fashion, skincare, or personal care routines.

Influencing future aspirations

Many children now say they aspire to become influencers when they grow up. According to surveys (for instance Morning Consult, 2023), being a social media influencer is seen by many as a “dream job.” The allure lies in the perceived fame, freedom, creativity, and financial success that influencers appear to enjoy.

Impact on worldview and values

Children spend significant amounts of time watching or interacting with influencers, sometimes several hours a day. This repeated exposure shapes their worldview and perceptions of success, beauty, and social norms. Influencer content is often highly curated and idealized, yet many children lack the media literacy skills to recognize these manipulations. As a result, they may develop unrealistic expectations or skewed values.

Conflicting values: influencers vs. traditional role models

Another key consideration is helping kids recognize and reflect on the values promoted by influencers compared to those conveyed by traditional role models such as parents and other family members. While family members often model values like responsibility, empathy, perseverance, and integrity through daily interactions, influencers highlight values more aligned with consumer culture, such as popularity, beauty, success, or material wealth. This contrast can confuse young adolescents who are still developing their sense of identity and moral compass.

Building critical awareness in kids

Because influencers often present curated lifestyles that appear glamorous and easy to attain, children may begin to prioritize external validation, image, or fame over more grounded and meaningful personal development. By encouraging kids to examine the messages and values they absorb online critically, educators can help them better differentiate between authentic values that contribute to

long-term well-being and superficial ideals that may lead to disappointment or unrealistic expectations.

Understanding influencer types

Understanding the types of influencers can help educators navigate this landscape more effectively. Influencers are typically categorized based on their number of followers (Kay, Mulcahy, Parkinson, 2020):

- Micro-influencers (up to 100,000 followers): Known for strong engagement and relatability.
- Macro-influencers (100,000 to 1 million followers): Professional content creators with broad reach.
- Mega-influencers (over 1 million followers): Often celebrities with professionally managed accounts.

Examples include MrBeast (YouTube), Khaby Lame (TikTok), and Cristiano Ronaldo (Instagram).

Educators' role in guiding digital literacy

Educators must be aware of influencers' immense power over young minds. While many influencers offer positive, educational, or entertaining content, others may promote unrealistic lifestyles, inappropriate behaviors, or consumerist values. The line between personal content and advertising is often blurred, and children may not always understand when they are being marketed to.

Emotional and psychological effects

It is also important to recognize the emotional and psychological impact influencers can have. Young adolescents are in a crucial stage of identity development, and social comparison is a normal but vulnerable aspect of this period. Constant exposure to filtered, polished images of success and happiness can lead to lowered self-esteem, anxiety, and dissatisfaction.

Promoting critical thinking and balance

However, this digital landscape also offers opportunities for learning and engagement. Some influencers promote educational content, body positivity, mental health awareness, and social activism. By guiding kids to critically analyze and evaluate the media they consume, educators can help them become media-literate digital citizens. A balanced approach is essential. Rather than demonizing influencers or banning social media discussions, educators should encourage open conversations about the content kids consume. These can help kids reflect on their media habits, explore the influence of digital content on their values and aspirations, and learn to navigate the digital world with critical thinking and self-awareness.

HOW THE UNIT WORKS

Topic 1: Importance of values

Values are guiding principles that influence how people interact with the world around them, impacting their choices and relationships. Different values, such as honesty, respect, and empathy, play a critical role in fostering a positive environment and guiding ethical behavior. By understanding the significance of these values, individuals can reflect on what is important in their lives. The exploration of values also sets the stage for examining the influence of both digital and traditional role models in promoting these essential principles.

What will the participants learn?

Upon completing this unit, kids will gain a comprehensive understanding of values and their critical role in shaping personal behavior and decision-making. They will be equipped to articulate their core values and reflect on how these principles influence their interactions and relationships. Furthermore, kids will explore various categories of values, discussing specific examples that illustrate their significance. This knowledge will empower kids to recognize the impact of values in their lives and the broader context of their social environment, fostering a deeper sense of self-awareness and ethical understanding.

Learning outcomes

The kids will be able to:

- define what values,
- explain the importance of values in guiding personal behavior and decision-making,
- identify and articulate their core values, reflecting on how these values influence their actions and relationships with others
- categorize various types of values and discuss examples of each.

Space configuration

It is not important how the participants sit in the room, it is important that they feel comfortable discussing personal values. In some situations, they will feel more comfortable sitting in a circle, and in other situations at their school desks. It is recommended that educators choose the way they assess that their kids will feel best. What is important for this activity is to place a sufficiently large table in the middle of the room on which to arrange the cards with the values. At the same time placing the table in the middle of the room will allow kids to circulate the table freely.

Methods and pedagogical techniques used

- Pre-comprehension and explanation
- Individual activities
- Full group activities

Tools

- Computers or tablets with internet access
- Monitor or projector
- PPT presentation
- Cards with values

Overview of the activities

Activity 1.a.1 – Exploring values in our lives

Kids reflect on the role of values in their personal lives. Through individual and group activities, they identify key values that guide behavior and decisions. The activity helps kids understand how values influence identity, relationships, and life choices.

Activity 1.a.2 – Identifying values behind role models

Kids analyze the values promoted by various traditional and digital role models. By reflecting critically on admired figures, kids learn to recognize both positive and negative influences and to evaluate role models based on meaningful personal values.

Detailed step-by-step instructions for the activities are provided in Activity Plan in the Annex.

Topic 2: Comparing traditional and digital role models

Role models play a significant part in shaping the values, attitudes, and aspirations of young people. In today's world, traditional role models such as parents and educators are joined by digital influencers who reach vast audiences through social media platforms. While both types of role models can inspire, teach, and influence behavior, they differ in how they communicate values, the mediums they use, and the type of influence they exert. This subunit delves into the similarities and differences between traditional and digital role models, examining the values they represent and the impact they have on young audiences. Through a series of activities, kids will explore the values promoted by these role models, critically analyze how these values are communicated, and reflect on how digital influencers may shape perceptions of body image and lifestyle. By fostering awareness and critical thinking, this activity aims to equip kids with the skills to evaluate role models in their lives and make thoughtful choices about whom they look up to and why.

What will the participants learn?

By exploring the values promoted by traditional and digital role models, kids will gain a comprehensive understanding of how these figures influence attitudes, behaviors, and perceptions. Through activities focused on critical analysis, kids will refine their ability to evaluate the credibility and intentions of both traditional and digital influencers. They will develop the capacity to recognize authentic values that align with their personal beliefs while questioning the societal and commercial motivations behind certain messages. By reflecting on the influence of digital role models on body image and lifestyle choices, kids will strengthen their self-awareness and ability to make thoughtful, value-driven decisions.

Learning outcomes

Kids will be able to:

- identify and compare the core values promoted by traditional role models and digital influencers, recognizing both similarities and differences in their messages,
- develop critical thinking skills to evaluate the authenticity, intentions, and impact of values communicated by both traditional and digital role models,
- reflect on personal beliefs and values, assessing how external influences, particularly from digital influencers, shape their perceptions of self-image and lifestyle choices,
- practice analytical and decision-making skills to determine which role models align with their own values and provide positive, meaningful inspiration in their lives.

Space configuration

The space should allow for activities in pairs and have a projector or monitor for projecting contents.

Methods and pedagogical techniques

The methods used in this phase will include:

- Pre-comprehension and explanation
- Individual and group activities
- Group discussion

Tools

- Computers or tablets
- PPT presentation
- monitor or projector
- worksheets

Overview of the activities

Activity 2.a.1 – Comparing traditional and digital role models

Kids compare traditional role models (such as parents, educators, historical figures) with digital role models (such as influencers and online celebrities). Through discussion and analysis, kids explore similarities and differences in the values, visibility, and influence of role models in different environments.

Activity 2.a.2 – Digital role models and social comparison

This activity focuses on the effects of digital role models on self-image and social comparison. Kids reflect on how online figures shape aspirations, perceptions of success, and personal identity. The activity encourages critical thinking about the pressures created by curated digital lives.

Activity 2.b.1 – Viral challenge match-up

Kids explore the phenomenon of viral challenges on social media. By examining popular examples, they identify motivations, risks, and societal impacts associated with viral trends. The activity encourages kids to think critically about participating in or sharing viral content.

Activity 2.b.2 – Challenge accepted? Evaluating safety in viral trends

Kids reflect on peer pressure and personal decision-making in the context of viral challenges. Through discussions and simulations, they practice assertiveness skills and learn to assess the potential consequences of accepting or rejecting challenges.

Activity 2.b.3 – Debunking influencer and viral challenges myths

In this activity, kids develop critical thinking skills by investigating common myths about influencers and viral challenges. By analyzing real examples, they learn to distinguish reality from exaggeration and marketing strategies. The activity promotes responsible media consumption.

Detailed step-by-step instructions for the activities are provided in Activity Plan in the Annex.

ACTIVITY PLANS & WORKSHEETS

Activity 1.a.1 – EXPLORING VALUES IN OUR LIVES

Objective

- To help students recognize and reflect on the core values that are important in their own lives.
- To develop students' understanding of how values guide behaviors, decisions, and admiration for role models.
- To prepare students for deeper reflection on the values represented by traditional and digital role models.

Preparation

- Arrange the classroom in a circle or small groups to encourage open discussion.
- Create an open and relaxed environment.
- Whiteboard or flipchart for listing values.
- Markers or pens.
- Working materials:
 - Printable Worksheet 1: "My Values Reflection Sheet" (one per student).
 - Printable template - Value Cards: Cards with individual values written on them (e.g., honesty, kindness, creativity, leadership, popularity, loyalty, courage, respect, responsibility, fun, fairness). Print a set of value cards (one set per small group or a shared set for the class).
 - A master list of values to display or project during the activity (optional)

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- **Explain the objective:** "Today we'll think about the values that are important to us and how they influence our behavior, choices, and role models we admire."
- **Key ideas to introduce:**

- **Values** are ideas or beliefs about what is important in life.
 - Values influence who we look up to and how we behave.
 - **Warm-up question:**
"What are some qualities you admire in people you look up to?"
-

2. Practical Exercise – Identifying Personal Values (20 minutes)

Step 1: Group setup

- Divide students into small groups (4–6 participants) or keep them in a full circle, depending on class size.
- Give each group a set of **Value Cards**.

Step 2: Value Card Selection (10 minutes)

- Ask each student to:
 - Look at the set of value cards.
 - Choose **5 values** they feel are most important to them personally.
- Once everyone has selected their 5 cards, ask them to:
 - Narrow it down further to **3 core values** they would never want to lose.
- Students can write their selected values on **Worksheet 1**.

Step 3: Group sharing (10 minutes)

- Invite each student to share:
 - One value they chose and why it is important to them.
 - Encourage respectful listening without judgment.
-

3. Reflection and Discussion (10 minutes)

- Facilitate a discussion using these prompts:
 - "Were there any values that many people in the group chose?"
 - "Were there any surprising or unique values chosen?"
 - "How do you think these values influence the choices you make every day?"
 - "Do you think the people you admire most share these same values?"
- Summarize key learning points:
 - Everyone has different values, and that's okay.
 - Our values guide how we behave and who we admire.
 - Recognizing our own values helps us choose positive role models.

Concluding the activity

1. Recap of key learnings

- Values are central to who we are.
- Understanding our personal values helps us make better choices in life and online.
- Role models often reflect the values we find important.

2. Personal reflection

Ask students individually:

- "How can you live one of your chosen values more consciously this week?"

3. Group sharing

Invite a few students to share a small action they can take to live one of their values more actively.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

Display this message:

"Your values are your guide. Choose them carefully and live them proudly."

Optional next steps

Home assignment

Students can create a "Values Collage" using magazines, drawings, or digital images representing their core values.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1.a.1 - Exploring Values in Our Lives

Worksheet 1 (to be printed): My Core Values

List 5 values that are important to you.

From the list, choose your top 3 core values.

For each core value, write one example of how you show this value in real life.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1.a.1 - Exploring Values in Our Lives

Value Cards (to be printed and cut)

Welth

Faith

Benevolence

Humour

Closeness

Care

Welth

Communication

Love

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1.a.1 - Exploring Values in Our Lives

Value Cards (to be printed and cut)

Individuality

Truth

Kindness

Beauty

Loyalty

Attention

Dedication

Praise

Imagination

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1.a.1 - Exploring Values in Our Lives

Value Cards (to be printed and cut)

Peace

Family

Responsibility

Trust

Support

Comprehension

Safety

Optimism

Justice

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1.a.1 - Exploring Values in Our Lives

Value Cards (to be printed and cut)

Friendship

Honesty

Cooperation

Mutual effort

Openness

Empathy

Cordiality

Success

Creativity

Self-respect

Perseverance

Solidarity

Wisdom

Dignity

Generosity

Trustworthiness

Optimism

Humility

Courage

Bravery

Patience

Creativity

Curiosity

Honesty

Integrity

Loyalty

Gratitude

Fairness

Cooperation

Self-control

Kindness

Open-mindedness

Empathy

Compassion

Justice

Tolerance

Forgiveness

Respect

Responsibility

Activity 1.a.2 – IDENTIFYING VALUES BEHIND ROLE MODELS

Objective

Students will develop their critical thinking skills by identifying and analyzing the specific values promoted by different types of role models, both traditional and digital. Through individual reflection and group discussion, students will become more aware of the messages conveyed by admired figures and reflect on the importance of choosing role models who inspire positive personal development.

Preparation

- Prepare **Worksheet 1: Identifying Values Behind Role Models 1**
 - Add names of Role Models to the table (students choose or are given examples)
 - Values promoted by the role model (chosen from a provided list or written freely).
- Prepare a list of example role models (optional), including traditional figures (e.g., a favorite teacher, a community leader) and digital figures (e.g., a YouTuber, an Instagram influencer).
- Prepare a list of values for students to select from (e.g., perseverance, fame, kindness, responsibility, wealth, resilience, creativity, honesty, appearance, popularity).
- Prepare **Worksheet 2: Identifying Values Behind Role Models 2**

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction and Discussion (5–7 minutes)

- Start with a simple question to the class:
"What makes someone a good role model in your opinion?"
- Brainstorm answers and list a few values or qualities on the board.

Explain that the purpose of the activity is not just to admire someone, but to think critically about what messages or behaviors they are promoting — intentionally or unintentionally.

2. Group Activity 2 (10 minutes)

- Distribute **Worksheet 1** to each student.
- Instruct students to mark the values they believe are represented by each of the listed traditional and digital role models in the worksheet:
 - **Traditional role models:** Parents, Class Teacher, Best Friend
 - **Digital role models:** for example MrBeast, Khaby Lame, Charlie D’Amelio, Taylor Swift – add two names the group chooses and write them in the table
- After completing the worksheet, pair up students to:
 - Compare their answers.
 - Discuss why they marked certain values for each role model.

3. Individual Reflection (10–15 minutes)

- Distribute **Worksheet 2** to each student.

Task:

- Students select 3 role models (either from the list or their own ideas).
- For each role model, they identify 2–3 key values that the role model promotes.
- Students can use the list of sample values or come up with their own.

Guiding questions while students work:

- What does this person show as important through their actions, words, or lifestyle?
- Are these values positive, neutral, or negative?
- Do you agree with the values they promote?

Encourage students to think beyond surface-level impressions.

4. Pair Sharing and Group Discussion (10–15 minutes)

- After students complete their worksheets, invite them to form pairs.

In pairs:

- Compare and discuss the values they identified.
- Are there any surprising or questionable values?

Whole class reflection:

- What values appeared most often?
- Are traditional role models and digital role models promoting the same kinds of values?
- Which values are rare but important?

Encourage respectful discussion and highlight that role models can have both positive and negative influences.

Concluding the activity

- Summarize key learning points:
 - Being aware of the values behind admired figures helps in making conscious choices about who we follow or look up to.
 - Not every famous or popular person promotes positive values — it's important to think critically about influence.

Final reflection prompt to be displayed

"Choose one role model you admire. What value do they promote that you would like to strengthen in yourself?"

Students can share their answers aloud or write them down individually.

Follow-up

Students create a simple "Value Star" poster for one role model they admire.

The poster should include:

- The name of the role model
- Three key values this role model represents
- A short explanation of how each value is demonstrated in their actions

These posters can later be displayed in class to celebrate positive values and inspire critical discussion.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1a2: Identifying values behind role models

Worksheet 1 (to be printed)

Mark the values you think these people possess.

	Your parents	Your best friend			
KINDNESS					
HONESTY					
CREATIVITY					
COURAGE					
RESPECT					
FRIENDSHIP					
RESPONSIBILITY					
FUN					
HELPING OTHERS					
FAIRNESS					
CONFIDENCE					

This material has been developed within the Erasmus+ project ASAP - A Systemic Approach to social media and pre-adolescents through thinking skills education

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Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 1a2: Identifying values behind role models

Worksheet 2 (to be printed)

Task:

Select 3 role models of your choice

For each role model, identify 2-3 key values that the role model promotes.

Name of the role model:

Name of the role model:

Name of the role model:

Values of the role model:

Values of the role model:

Values of the role model:

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Role models

MrBeast (Jimmy Donaldson)	Greta Thunberg
Charli D'Amelio	Olivia Rodrigo
Khaby Lame	The Rock (Dwayne Johnson)
Emma Chamberlain	Dixie D'Amelio
Kai Cenat	Jude Bellingham
Alix Earle	Bella Poarch
Mark Rober	Addison Rae
IShowSpeed (Darren Watkins Jr.)	Ryan Trahan
Zendaya	Liza Koshy
Tom Holland	Taylor Swift

Values

Honesty
Kindness
Respect
Responsibility
Empathy
Fairness
Integrity
Courage
Generosity
Perseverance
Humility
Loyalty
Patience
Gratitude
Justice

Compassion
Forgiveness
Tolerance
Creativity
Cooperation
Self-control
Open-mindedness
Optimism
Dignity
Self-respect
Wisdom
Trustworthiness
Bravery
Curiosity
Solidarity

Choose one role model you admire.

What value do they promote that you would like to strengthen in yourself?

Activity 2.a.1 – SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES BETWEEN TRADITIONAL AND DIGITAL ROLE MODELS

Objective

Students will explore the concept of role models by comparing traditional role models (such as family members, teachers, historical figures) with digital role models (such as influencers, streamers, or online celebrities). Through discussion and critical thinking, students will identify similarities and differences between the two types of role models and reflect on how the medium (offline or online) influences the way role models are perceived and followed.

Preparation

- Prepare **Worksheet: Similarities and differences between traditional and digital role models**, divided into three sections:
 - Values common to both types.
 - Values specific to traditional role models.
 - Values specific to digital role models.
 - Prepare a list of example values (e.g., kindness, ambition, creativity, beauty, fame, leadership, responsibility).
 - Arrange students into pairs or small groups (2–4 students).
 - Prepare a few examples of traditional and digital role models to start the discussion (optional).
-

Step-by-step instructions

1. Warm-up Discussion (5–7 minutes)

- Begin by asking students:
"Who is a person you admire in real life?"
"Who is someone you admire online?"
- Write some examples on the board.
- Briefly introduce the difference between **traditional** and **digital** role models.

Explain that while both types can inspire us, the way they influence us and the values they promote can be different because of how we interact with them.

2. Group Work – Comparison (15–20 minutes)

- Divide students into pairs or small groups.
- Distribute **Worksheet 1** to each group.

Task:

- In the first section of the worksheet, students list **5–10 values** or qualities they believe both traditional and digital role models share.
- In the second section, students list values typically associated with traditional role models.
- In the third section, they list values often promoted by digital role models.

Guiding Questions to support students:

- What makes someone a role model, regardless of where we know them from?
- How does being famous online change the type of values a person promotes?
- Are traditional role models more connected to real life?

Encourage students to discuss differences in **visibility**, **accessibility**, **authenticity**, and **commercialization** between traditional and digital figures.

3. Sharing and Reflection (10–15 minutes)

- Each group shares their main points with the class.
- Summarize on the board:
 - Common values across both types.
 - Unique characteristics or risks in digital role models.

Facilitate a class discussion using questions like:

- "Are there values we expect more from traditional role models than from digital ones?"
 - "Do you think it's easier to become a digital role model than a traditional one? Why?"
-

Concluding the activity

- Highlight key learning points:
 - Both traditional and digital role models can inspire positive growth — or promote superficial values.
 - The platform and medium shape how we perceive and follow role models.
- Reinforce the idea that being a role model (whether online or offline) carries responsibility.

Final reflection prompt:

"If you could choose one value that every role model should promote, what would it be — and why?"

Students can share briefly in class or write their choice in their journals or on a sticky note.

Follow-up

Task

At home, students choose one traditional and one digital role model they admire.

They write a short paragraph (5–7 sentences) comparing what values each person promotes and reflecting on which one they would prefer to follow and why.

Encourage students to bring their paragraphs back to the next lesson for optional sharing or use in a display about positive role models.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2a1: Comparing traditional and digital role models

Worksheet (to be printed)

Activity 2.a.2 – DIGITAL ROLE MODELS AND SOCIAL COMPARISON

Objective

- To help students reflect on how digital role models and influencers affect self-esteem and self-perception.
- To raise awareness of social comparison processes triggered by curated online content.
- To encourage critical thinking about the realities behind influencer lifestyles.

Preparation

- Traditional classroom setup facing a screen (for video viewing).
- Flexible space for small group discussion afterward.
- Select or prepare a short, appropriate video clip of influencers showing an idealized lifestyle (e.g., travel vloggers, fitness influencers, beauty TikTokers). Make sure it's non-controversial and school-appropriate. Choose influencer that currently resonates among the students of your class. Suggestions:
 - Dove Reverse Selfie: Social Media's Impact on Girls' Self-Esteem - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z2T-Rh838GA>
 - Dove Toxic Influence: Mothers & Daughters Confront Toxic Social Media - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sF3iRZtkyAQ&t=1s>
 - Dove Campaign for Real Beauty - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wpM499XhMJQ>
- Printable Worksheet 1: "Social Comparison Reflection Sheet" (one per student).
- Whiteboard or flipchart and markers.
- Alternatively, use screenshots or social media posts if video is not available.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- **Explain the objective:** "Today we'll explore how social media and digital role models can influence how we see ourselves and others."
 - **Key ideas to introduce:**
 - **Social comparison** happens when we compare ourselves to others.
 - Seeing only the *best moments* of someone else's life can make us feel dissatisfied with our own.
 - **Warm-up question:**
"Have you ever seen a post online that made you wish your life was more exciting or different? What was it?"
-

2. Practical Exercise – Video Viewing and Reflection (20 minutes)

Step 1: Video Viewing (5 minutes)

- Play the short influencer video.
- Ask students to simply watch and note their feelings and reactions without judgment.

Step 2: Personal Reflection (5 minutes)

- Distribute Worksheet 1.
- Students answer reflection questions individually:
 - How did this video make you feel about your own life?
 - Did anything make you feel inspired, jealous, left out, motivated?
 - What do you think is missing from the video about real life?

Step 3: Group Discussion (10 minutes)

- In small groups (3–5 students), discuss:
 - What emotions did the video trigger?
 - Why do influencers often show only their best moments?
 - How can this affect the way people see themselves?
 - What are some *real-life challenges* that are usually not shown online?
-

3. Reflection and Whole Class Discussion (10 minutes)

- Facilitate a group discussion using prompts:
 - "Do you think influencers' lives are as perfect as they appear online? Why or why not?"
 - "How can you remind yourself that online life is often only a highlight reel?"
 - "What can you do when you notice yourself comparing your life to others online?"

- Summarize key learning points:
 - Social media often shows only curated parts of life.
 - Comparison to these curated images can lower self-esteem.
 - Being aware of this can protect your mental health and encourage gratitude for your real life.

Concluding the activity

1. Recap of key learnings

- Digital role models show curated, often unrealistic images of their lives.
- Social comparison can affect self-esteem and self-perception.
- Awareness helps in developing a healthier, more balanced view of oneself.

2. Personal reflection

Ask students individually:

- "Next time you see a perfect post online, what will you remind yourself about it?"

3. Group sharing

Invite a few students to share:

- A strategy they could use to resist negative social comparison.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

Display this message:

"Your life is real — not a highlight reel. Celebrate it."

Optional next steps

Creative homework

Students create a "Real Life vs. Online Life" poster showing the difference between reality and curated social media images.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2a2: Digital role models and social comparison

Worksheet 1 (to be printed): Social Comparison Reflection Sheet

Reflect honestly on how social media influences your feelings about yourself and others.

Question	Student's response
How did this video make you feel about your own life?	
Did anything make you feel inspired, jealous, left out, motivated?	
What is missing from this video about real life??	
What emotions did the video trigger?	
Why do influencers often show only their best moments?	
How can this affect the way people see themselves?	
What are some real-life challenges that are usually not shown online?	

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2a2: Digital role models and social comparison

To be displayed

**Your life is real — not a highlight reel.
Celebrate it.**

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Activity 2.b.1 – VIRAL CHALLENGE MATCH-UP

Objective

- To introduce students to the phenomenon of viral challenges and how they spread through social media.
- To develop students' ability to distinguish between harmless and dangerous viral challenges.
- To encourage critical thinking and personal responsibility when engaging with online trends.
- To foster discussion about peer influence, risk-taking, and digital citizenship.

Preparation

- Arrange tables for small group collaboration (3–5 students per group).
- Print sets of the Match-up cards - one for for each group. Cut the worksheet into individual cards with the names of the challenges and their descriptions. Prepare envelopes to keep the card sets organized for each group. Organize students into small groups of 3–5 at desks to foster teamwork and discussion.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- Begin the lesson by briefly introducing the concept of viral challenges, highlighting how they spread on social media and influence youth participation. Emphasize that while some challenges are fun and meaningful, others can be harmful or even dangerous. When explaining viral challenges, use the challenge description provided in the theoretical description of the entire learning unit.
- **Warm-up question:**
"Have you ever seen or participated in a viral challenge? What was it?"

2. Practical Exercise – Challenge Match-up (10 minutes)

Step 1: Group work

- Explain that students will play a matching game to connect the names of viral challenges with their descriptions. Each group will receive a set of challenge cards and matching descriptions. The goal is to correctly pair each challenge with its description, then sort the paired challenges into two categories: harmless and dangerous. Remind students to think critically about the potential impact of each challenge on participants' safety and well-being.
- Hand out one set of cut cards to each group. Allow 10–15 minutes for students to pair the challenges with their descriptions. Circulate the classroom to observe and guide groups if they have questions. Once groups complete their matches, ask them to sort the challenges into two categories: harmless and dangerous. Have them place the cards in two piles or create two columns on their desks for easy visualization.

Step 2: Group discussion (15 minutes)

- Prompt groups to discuss which challenges they already knew about, which ones surprised them, and whether they or someone they know has participated in any of the challenges. If students feel comfortable, invite them to share if they have participated in any viral challenges or witnessed others doing so. Discuss the reasons for participating and the outcomes.
- Invite each group to share their sorting results and explain their reasoning for categorizing specific challenges as harmless or dangerous. Encourage further discussion using the following questions:
 - Were there any challenges you thought were harmless but realized could be dangerous after this activity?
 - What influences people, especially young people, to participate in viral challenges?
 - How do social media platforms contribute to the spread of these challenges?

Concluding the activity

1. Recap of key learnings

- Reinforce the difference between harmless and dangerous challenges, emphasizing the importance of making informed decisions.
- Highlight how peer pressure and social media trends can influence behavior and encourage students to think critically before participating in viral challenges.

2. Personal reflection

Ask students individually: "What will you think about next time you see a viral challenge online?"

Optional next steps

Task:

Students work in pairs to find examples of positive viral challenges (e.g., challenges that promote kindness, health, or creativity) and prepare a 2-minute oral presentation or a short written description.

Examples could include:

- The Ice Bucket Challenge (raising awareness for ALS).
- #Trashtag Challenge (cleaning the environment).

THE ICE BUCKET CHALLENGE

Two people convince another person to jump and then kick their legs out, causing the person jumping to fall on their head.

THE RENEGADE DANCE CHALLENGE

You are watching funny videos or compilations while attempting to resist laughter.

Women shared pictures of themselves without makeup to raise awareness of breast cancer.

THE SKULL- BREAKER CHALLENGE

Individuals pour a bucket of ice-cold water over themselves to raise awareness and funds for amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS).

THE CINNAMON CHALLENGE

TRY NOT TO LAUGH CHALLENGE

Viral dance performed on the social media platform TikTok, where people dance to the song Lottery by K Camp.

THE BIRD BOX CHALLENGE

Involving the growing of mustaches during November to raise awareness of men's health issues.

MOVEMBER CHALLENGE

Individuals film themselves completing everyday tasks blindfolded.

THE PENNY/ OUTLET CHALLENGE

The challenge requires people to drive to the rhythm of DJ Casper's song "Cha Cha Slide".

Individuals attempting to swallow a spoonful of cinnamon without drinking any liquids.

NO MAKEUP SELFIE CHALLENGE

Putting phone chargers halfway into outlets and dropping coins onto the exposed prongs to create sparks.

THE CHA CHA SLIDE CHALLENGE

Activity 2.b.2 – CHALLENGE ACCEPTED? EVALUATING SAFETY IN VIRAL TRENDS

Objective

- To teach students how to critically evaluate viral challenges before participating.
- To build risk-assessment skills and promote safe behavior online.
- To empower students to make informed decisions and resist peer pressure.

Preparation

- Arrange tables for small group discussions (3–5 students per group).
- Printable Worksheet 1: "Viral Challenge Safety Checklist" (one per group or individual).
- Markers or pens.
- (Optional) Poster board for creating "Safety Rules for Online Challenges."
- Poster or slide showing examples of **risk factors** to consider (e.g., physical danger, legal issues, emotional impact, peer pressure). See Worksheet 2.

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- **Explain the objective:** "Today we'll learn how to think carefully before accepting or promoting a viral challenge. Not every challenge is safe just because it's popular!"
- **Key ideas to introduce:**
 - Always **assess** the risks before participating.
 - **Peer pressure** can make risky challenges seem harmless.
 - **Smart decision-making** protects yourself and others.
- **Warm-up question:**
"What are some questions you should ask yourself before doing something risky online?"

2. Practical Exercise – Evaluating Challenges (20 minutes)

Step 1: Group setup

- Divide students into small groups (3–5 participants).
- Distribute Worksheet 1 to each group.

Step 2: Group work (15 minutes)

- Each group will:
 - Review the viral challenges on the Worksheet.
 - For each challenge, answer the Safety Checklist questions:
 - Is there a physical danger?
 - Could it harm someone else?
 - Could it damage property?
 - Could it get me in trouble (with parents, school, law)?
 - Am I doing it just because of peer pressure?
 - What are the real benefits and risks?
- Mark each challenge as **Safe**, **Unsafe**, or **Needs More Information**.

Challenge suggestions:

Challenge Name	Description	Type
Ice Bucket Challenge	Pouring a bucket of ice water over yourself to raise awareness for ALS.	Harmless
Mannequin Challenge	Freezing in place like mannequins while a video is recorded.	Harmless
Planking Challenge	Lying flat like a plank in unusual locations.	Harmless (with caution)
Harlem Shake	Dancing wildly in a group to a specific song.	Harmless
Bottle Cap Challenge	Kicking the cap off a bottle without knocking over the bottle.	Harmless
Tide Pod Challenge	Biting into detergent pods, which is poisonous.	Dangerous

Skull Breaker Challenge	Tripping someone while they jump in the air, causing injury.	Dangerous
Fire Challenge	Setting oneself on fire and filming it.	Dangerous
Blue Whale Challenge	A dangerous "game" encouraging self-harm.	Dangerous
Cinnamon Challenge	Eating a spoonful of cinnamon in one minute without drinking water, risking choking.	Dangerous

Step 3: Group decision

- Each group creates a simple "**Challenge Decision Rule**" — one sentence that sums up how they will decide whether to accept or reject a viral challenge in the future.

3. Group Discussion (10 minutes)

- Invite each group to share:
 - One challenge they evaluated.
 - Their **Challenge Decision Rule**.
- Discuss:
 - "What was surprising about the risks you found?"
 - "Why is it harder to say no when friends or influencers encourage a challenge?"
 - "How can you help a friend think twice before doing something risky?"
- Summarize key learning points:
 - A cool challenge is never worth serious harm.
 - Thinking critically before acting is a sign of strength, not weakness.

Concluding the activity

1. Recap of key learnings

- Viral challenges can carry hidden risks.
- Careful evaluation protects yourself and others.
- Your safety matters more than popularity.

2. Personal reflection

Ask students individually:

- "What will you do if you feel pressured to join a challenge that feels unsafe?"

3. Group sharing

Invite a few students to share:

- One piece of advice they would give to a friend about viral challenges.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

Display this message:

"Be smart. Stay safe. Think before you challenge."

Optional next steps

Creative homework

Students design a "Think Before You Challenge" poster with their own safety rule.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2b2: Challenge accepted

Worksheet 1 (to be printed): Viral Challenge Safety Checklist

Task:

Use this checklist to decide whether a viral challenge is safe to join. Be honest and critical.

Challenge	Is there a physical danger?	Could it harm someone else?	Could it damage property?	Could it get me in trouble?	Am I doing it just because of peer pressure?	What are the real benefits and risks?	Safe? Dangerous? Need more info?
Ice Bucket Challenge							
Mannequin Challenge							
Tide Pod Challenge							
Skull Breaker Challenge							
Fire Challenge							
Blue Whale Challenge							
Cinnamon Challenge							

Challenge Decision Rule:

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**Be smart.
Stay safe.
Think before you challenge.**

Activity 2.b.3 – DEBUNKING INFLUENCER AND VIRAL CHALLENGES MYTHS

Objective

- To help students critically evaluate information about influencers and viral challenges.
- To teach students how to identify myths, exaggerations, and misinformation.
- To strengthen students' critical thinking and digital literacy skills.

Preparation

- Tables for small group collaboration (3–5 students per group).
- Printable Worksheet 1: "Debunking Myths: True or False?" (one per student or group).
- Prepared list of myths about influencers: 10–12 short statements (some true, some false) related to influencers, social media life, and viral challenges.
- Markers or pens.
- A slide "**How to Spot a Myth**" with tips (e.g., too extreme to be true, no source, appeals only to emotion, peer-shared without checking).

Step-by-step instructions

1. Introduction (5 minutes)

- **Explain the objective:** "Today we'll learn how to spot myths about influencers and viral challenges — and think before we believe or share information."
- **Key ideas to introduce:**
 - Not everything we hear about influencers or viral challenges is true.
 - Myths can spread quickly because they are emotional, shocking, or funny.
- **Warm-up question:** "Have you ever believed something online that later turned out to be fake or exaggerated?"

2. Practical Exercise – Myth Debunking Game (20 minutes)

Step 1: Group setup

- Divide students into small groups (3–5 participants).
- Distribute Worksheet 1 to each group.

Step 2: Group work (15 minutes)

- Read the 10 prepared statements aloud or display them on the screen.
- For each statement, students decide:
 - **True** — Confirmed and verifiable.
 - **False** — Myth, fake, or exaggerated.
- Groups record their answers on Worksheet 1.
- After deciding, each group explains:
 - Why they thought it was true or false.
 - What clues helped them make their decision.

Correct answers:

- **1 Most influencers are experts in the challenges they promote.**
 - False – Many influencers participate in or promote challenges for popularity without being experts or understanding the risks.
- **2 All virtual challenges promoted by influencers are safe if many people participate.**
 - False – Even popular challenges can be dangerous or harmful.
- **3 You should always research a challenge before trying it, even if your favorite influencer recommends it.**
 - True – It's important to evaluate the risks of any challenge, no matter who is promoting it.
- **4 Some virtual challenges can lead to serious physical harm or legal consequences.**
 - True – Certain challenges have caused injuries, deaths, or legal trouble for participants.
- **5 Influencers may use tricks like editing or special effects to make challenges look easier or safer than they are.**
 - True – Many influencers edit their content, which can mislead viewers about the difficulty or risks involved in challenges.
- **6 It's okay to skip a challenge, even if everyone else is doing it.**
 - True – It's always important to prioritize your safety and well-being over fitting in with trends or challenges.
- **7 Some influencers promote challenges because they are paid by companies to do so.**
 - True – Influencers often collaborate with brands or companies and get paid to promote certain challenges or products.
- **8 It's easy to tell when a challenge is dangerous just by watching a video online.**
 - False – Many dangers might not be obvious from a video, such as hidden physical risks or social pressure.

- **9 Peer pressure from influencers or friends can make people feel like they need to join a challenge, even if they're unsure.**
 - True – Social pressure can make it difficult for people to say no to participating in challenges, even when they feel it might not be a good idea.
 - **10 Some challenges are specifically designed to encourage kindness or positive actions.**
 - True – There are many positive challenges, such as those promoting charity or community service.
-

3. Group Discussion (10 minutes)

- Invite each group to share:
 - One myth they found surprising.
 - One clue they used to spot a myth.
 - Use discussion prompts:
 - "Why do you think fake or exaggerated stories spread so easily?"
 - "What can you do when you hear something shocking or extreme online?"
 - "How can you check if a story about a viral trend is true?"
 - Summarize key points:
 - Always be skeptical of extreme, emotional, or peer-shared stories.
 - Double-check facts before believing or spreading information.
-

Concluding the activity

1. Recap of key learnings

- Myths about influencers and viral challenges spread fast — but we can learn to spot them.
- Critical thinking and fact-checking help protect ourselves and others.
- Being careful before sharing information online is part of being a responsible digital citizen.

2. Personal reflection

Ask students individually:

- "What is one thing you will do differently next time you hear a shocking story online?"

3. Group sharing

Invite a few students to share:

- A strategy they would recommend for spotting online myths.

4. Reinforce the takeaway

Display this message:

"Think twice. Share wise."

Optional next steps

Creative homework

Students design a meme or poster with a "Myth Buster Tip" for spotting fake news or exaggerated influencer stories.

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2b3: Debunking influencer and viral challenges myths

Worksheet 1 (to be printed): Debunking Myths: True or False

Task:

Decide if each statement is true or false. Write down one clue or reason that helped you decide.

Statement	True	False	Statement	True	False
Most influencers are experts in the challenges they promote.			It's okay to skip a challenge, even if everyone else is doing it.		
All virtual challenges promoted by influencers are safe if many people participate.			Some influencers promote challenges because they are paid by companies to do so.		
You should always research a challenge before trying it, even if your favorite influencer recommends it.			It's easy to tell when a challenge is dangerous just by watching a video online.		
Some virtual challenges can lead to serious physical harm or legal consequences.			Peer pressure from influencers or friends can make people feel like they need to join a challenge, even if they're unsure.		
Influencers may use tricks like editing or special effects to make challenges look easier or safer than they are.			Some challenges are specifically designed to encourage kindness or positive actions.		

Learning Unit: Role Models

Activity 2b3: Debunking influencer and viral challenges myths

Slide to be displayed

Think twice. Share wise.

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